

RISK ASSESSMENT & HAZARD ANALYSIS FORM

High Voltage Electric Vehicle Battery Repurposing

Location/Lab: _____

Procedure: (*e.g. battery extraction*) _____

Date: _____

1. PERSONNEL

List all individuals involved in this procedure.

Role	Name	Signature
Team Member 1:		
Team Member 2:		
Supervisor (PI):		

2. PRE-WORK CHECKLIST

About the Vehicle and Traction Battery

Vehicle type/model (*e.g. Toyota Prius*): _____

Voltage system (*e.g. 400V system*): _____

Battery voltage and capacity: _____

Work condition

If any of these are checked "YES", work **MUST NOT** proceed until mitigated or approved by the supervisor.

Condition	Yes	No	N/A
Training: Are any personnel untrained/uncertified for this work?			
PPE: Is required PPE damaged, missing, or expired?			
Tools: Are insulated tools unavailable?			
Equipment: Is any equipment defective?			
After Hours: Will work occur outside normal hours?			

3. HAZARD IDENTIFICATION

Check all risks associated with this specific procedure.

High Voltage / Electrical

Electrical Shock (>60V DC)

Arc Flash / Blast

Short Circuit potential

Physical / Mechanical

Heavy Lifting / Crush Hazard

Sharp Edges (Chassis/Metal)

Pinch Points

Falling Objects

Chemical / Thermal

Thermal Runaway

Explosion Potential

Electrolyte Leakage (Corrosive)

Hazardous Fumes/Venting

4. JOB HAZARD ANALYSIS MATRIX

Break down the procedure into steps. Identify the specific hazard for each step and the control measure required.

Step	Activity	Potential Hazard	Control Measures
1	<i>Work area preparation</i>	<i>Unauthorized entry</i>	<i>Barricades, Warning Signs, Buddy System</i>

5. REQUIRED PPE (Personal Protective Equipment)

Verify the following equipment is inspected and available.

Electrical Safety

Class 0 Voltage Rated Gloves (1kV)

Leather Protectors for Gloves

Arc Flash Face Shield

Arc Rated Clothing

[] Others _____

General Safety

[] Safety Glasses (ANSI Z87+) [] Steel-Toed Safety Boots (EH Rated)

[] Chemical Resistant Gloves (Nitrile - if checking leaks)

[] Others _____

6. EMERGENCY RESPONSE PLAN

Confirm the location and status of emergency equipment.

Equipment	Location Verified	Any notes
HV rescue hook		
Fire extinguisher		
Emergency eye wash		
Chemical spill kit		
Others:		

In case of Battery Fire:

1. Evacuate the area immediately
2. Activate the fire alarm.
3. Call Emergency Services: 111 in Rwanda
4. DO NOT use water on HV electrical fires unless trained to do so.

7. FINAL AUTHORIZATION

Assessor Statement:

I have assessed the risks associated with this procedure and have implemented the necessary controls.

Assessor Signature: _____ Date: _____

Supervisor Statement:

I verify that the assessor is competent to perform this work and that the safety measures proposed are adequate for the risk level involved.

Supervisor Signature: _____ Date: _____